

Recommended citation: De Laet, T., Sijmkens, E., & De Cock, M. (2021). Triggering reflection and meta-cognition in physics problem solving. In Heiß, H.-U., Järvinen, H.-M., Mayer, A., & Schulz, A. (Eds.), *Blended Learning in Engineering Education: challengingm enlightening and lasting? SEFI 49th Annual Conference* (pp. 180-188). European Society for Engineering Education (SEFI), Berlin, Germany. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14646973.

TRIGGERING REFLECTION AND META-COGNITION IN PHYSICS PROBLEM SOLVING

Tinne De Laet¹, Elien Sijmkens, Mieke De Cock

Leuven Engineering and Science Education Center, KU Leuven
Leuven, Belgium

0000-0003-0624-3305, 0000-0003-3653-6205, 0000-0002-2489-1528

Conference Key Areas: *Physics in engineering*

Keywords: *meta-cognition, self-regulation, mechanics, physics, problem-solving, conceptual learning*

ABSTRACT

Self-regulated learning strategies support learning. Recently, the Learning Companion, a tool carefully grounded in theory and designed to promote self-regulation while students solve engineering problems, was introduced by Tormey et al. The companion presents students with a standard questionnaire for each problem, including a predefined list of generic difficulties related to quantitative problem solving. Ample scientific research has, however, indicated that metacognition is most effective when it takes place in a domain-specific context. The goal of our research is to determine the feasibility and impact of a "Disciplinary Learning Companion" (DLC), building on topic-specific rather than generic questions.

In the paper we first present the DLC and connect it to the theoretical frameworks of self-regulation and metacognition. Second, we present a case study of the DLC executed within a 1st year mechanics course. On the quantitative side we connect the interaction of students with the DLC to their learning skills measured using a validated questionnaire and their academic achievement. On the qualitative side, we present the findings of interviews with teaching assistants. Based on the results we present recommendations regarding the further development and research around "disciplinary companions" to induce students' self-reflection when solving engineering problems.

¹ T. De Laet
tinne.delaet@kuleuven.be

1 INTRODUCTION

Self-regulated learning strategies support learning. Not only is there a strong theoretical support for this claim [3], also intervention studies have shown that self-regulation is associated with academic achievement [4]. Self-regulation is a widely-used term that, nevertheless, lacks a clear definition. Depending on the particular theoretical model consulted, it can focus on metacognition, i.e. ..., or also include elements of affect and motivation. [2]. Feedback is a potentially very powerful tool to impact learning and achievement, but different types of feedback can have different (levels) of impact [6]. Feedback can therefore also play a role in triggering of metacognition and self-reflection as Hattie and Timperley [6] state: “Feedback that attends to self-regulation is powerful to the degree that it leads to further engagement with or investing further effort into the task, to enhanced self-efficacy, and to attributions that the feedback is deserved and earned. When feedback draws attention to the regulatory processes needed to engage with a task, learners’ beliefs about the importance of effort and their conceptions of learning can be important moderators in the learning process.” One way to provide feedback is through Learning Analytics Dashboards [5]. They can provide a visual display of students self-regulation based on digital traces collected such as behavior in online learning environments or reflection tools, but also more “old-fashioned” data such as survey data or student background information can be used. Recently, the Learning Companion, a tool carefully grounded in theory and designed to promote self-regulation while students solve engineering problems, was introduced by Tormey et al [1]. The companion presents students with a standard questionnaire for each problem including a predefined list of generic difficulties related to quantitative problem solving. Ample scientific research has however indicated that metacognition is more effective when it takes place in a domain-specific context. Furthermore, feedback is more powerful when it supports the building cues and information regarding wrong hypotheses and ideas [6], which is potentially, and therefore part of our hypothesis, easier in domain-specific reflections. Next, developing particular conceptual knowledge in engineering subjects is difficult, not well-understood yet, but definitely requires particular attention [7]. The goal of our research is to determine the feasibility and impact of a "Disciplinary Learning Companion" (DLC), building on topic-specific questions rather than generic questions to trigger reflection with students during or after scientific problem solving.

The Disciplinary Learning Companion is clearly inspired by the EPFL Learning Companion [1], which was designed to improve students’ skills in problem solving in scientific and mathematical problems in the context of science and engineering degree programmes. In particular, the Disciplinary Learning Companion aims at offering an alternative to the “diary” of the EPFL Companion. This is the component where students reflect after they have worked on a set of mathematical problems in class (exercise sessions). Students then complete a standardised diary questionnaire in the EPFL Learning Companion for each problem, logging the number of problems they attempted, whether they succeeded or not as well as the difficulties they encountered in the process [1]. The questionnaire is called “standardised” as it is a predefined list of difficulties related to quantitative problem solving. As such, these questions do not relate to particularities of each question but rather address the more general processes of scientific problem solving. The Disciplinary Learning Companion on the contrary aims at offering students problem-

specific questions, in particular inspired by the conceptual difficulties in the domain at hand (mechanics in this paper) [7]. The focus on domain- and even course-specific (conceptual) difficulties contains the possibility for more topic-specific feedback related to the particular subject, which can have higher impact on students' learning and development. An obvious disadvantage of the problem-specific questions in the Disciplinary Learning Companion is the additional time needed for development of the reflection questions and the feedback, as they will have to be developed separately for each particular problem. With the Disciplinary Learning Companion we want to research whether the disciplinary-focus leads to higher impact on students' reflection and learning, and if this higher impact can justify the higher development cost. Additionally, to "manage" the development cost and to ensure quality of the problem-specific questions developed for the Disciplinary Learning Companion, we aim at developing a structured process and connected with that, guidelines that allow teaching teams to build these questions in co-creation while taking into account the research on domain-specific conceptual difficulties [7]. In this paper we present for the first time our idea of the Disciplinary Learning Companion, the five domains that aim to provide structure to the reflection connected to a specific problem, the theoretical foundation of the learning companion, and the results of a first pilot.

2 DISCIPLINARY LEARNING COMPANION: WHAT AND WHY?

2.1 What is the Disciplinary Learning Companion?

The goal of the Disciplinary Learning Companion is to make students reflect on scientific problems they are typically solving in the context of a higher-education science course. The Disciplinary Learning Companion is a self-reflection tool that students use independently during or after they solved a single problem or a set of problems, and that presents problem-specific questions and feedback to trigger the students' reflection. We identified, based on research on science problem solving, five key dimensions to structure the reflection questions: 1) Strategy Plan, focusing on the fact that students use a well-considered strategy to tackle the problem or not; 2) Concepts, focusing on the domain-specific concepts needed to solve the problem (e.g. developing a free-body diagram in mechanics); 3) Mathematical model, i.e. whether students can translate their conceptual understanding to mathematical formulas (e.g. equilibrium of forces); 4) Computations, i.e. whether students can correctly solve the mathematical model obtained; and 5) Interpretation, i.e. whether students can interpret the obtained solution (e.g. are the magnitude, sign, and units of my solution as expected?). Table 1 provides for each of the five dimensions an example of a reflection question from the Disciplinary Learning Companion used in the pilot of this paper (statics problem in a mechanics course).

Table 1: Example of reflection questions (statics problem in a mechanics course) from the Disciplinary Learning Companion used in the pilot of this paper for each of the five dimensions.

Strategy plan

Did you use a strategy plan to solve the question?

No, I did not have an explicit strategy plan:

- I did not make my plan explicit.*
- I did not have a strategy plan.*

Yes, I did have an explicit strategy plan consisting of:

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> <i>determining my strategy plan</i> <input type="checkbox"/> <i>splitting the problem in subproblems: in this case determining the center of gravity for the different bodies</i> <input type="checkbox"/> <i>solving subproblems: in this case combining the center of gravity of the different bodies into the center of gravity of the whole structure</i> <input type="checkbox"/> <i>reflect on the obtained result.</i> 	
<p>Concepts <i>Which of the following components were part of your free body diagram?</i></p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> <i>column</i> <input type="checkbox"/> <i>beam</i> <input type="checkbox"/> <i>ground</i></p>	<p>Mathematical model <i>How did you apply the generic formula $\vec{r}_c = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N \vec{r}_i m_i}{\sum_{i=1}^N m_i}$ to calculate the center of gravity of the whole structure from the centers of gravity of the different bodies to this particular context? (answers show possible elaborations of the formula, or the "I do not know option".</i></p>
<p>Computations <i>Were you able to calculate the center of gravity of the whole structure correctly from the mathematical model?</i></p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> <i>yes</i> <input type="checkbox"/> <i>no</i> <input type="checkbox"/> <i>I was not able to determine the mathematical model</i></p>	<p>Interpretation <i>Did you check if the obtained solution was feasible?</i></p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> <i>No</i> <i>Yes, I did the following</i> <input type="checkbox"/> <i>check the units of my solution</i> <input type="checkbox"/> <i>check if the obtained position is feasible both in sign (positive/negative) and in magnitude (e.g. center of gravity is within the outer dimensions of the whole structure)</i></p>

2.2 How is the Disciplinary Learning Companion grounded in theory?

Figure 1: The Metacognitive and Affective model of Self-Regulate Learning (MASRL) of Efklides [2]. MK= metacognitive knowledge, MS = metacognitive skills

We situate the Disciplinary Learning Companion in the Metacognitive and Affective model of Self-Regulate Learning (MASRL) of Efklides [2], also presented in Figure 1. The Disciplinary Learning Companion focuses on supporting the metacognitive monitoring and control (cognitive loop) in the Task x Person level of the MASRL model, where the specific task processing (cognition) occurs. In particular, the companion focuses at supporting the self-observation of students by providing external triggers (reflection questions and feedback in the companion). These triggers should induce internal metacognitive experiences. Supported by repeated application of the Disciplinary Learning Companion, these experiences hopefully

change the students' metacognitive knowledge (e.g. the five domains important for solving mechanics problems, or possible ways to interpret a solution of a problem) and metacognitive skills (e.g. reflecting on the strategy to tackle a problem, and interpreting the solution of a problem) at the Person level.

3 THE DISCIPLINARY LEARNING COMPANION IN ACTION

This section describes the implementation of a pilot of a Disciplinary Learning Companion implemented in the first semester of academic year 2020-2021 and formulates the research questions we answer in this paper.

3.1 Context

The pilot of the Disciplinary Learning Companion was organized around a mid-term test of the course Applied Mechanics, part 1 with first-year students of the Bachelor of Engineering Science and the Bachelor of Engineering Science, Architecture at KU Leuven in Belgium. Applied Mechanics, part 1 is a course where a rather limited set of theory should be acquired to solve simplified but realistic engineering problems related to statics, kinematics, and dynamics. Based on the success rate of students, this course is the hardest course of the first-year, resulting in a typical pass rate of 40% (without resit). To support the first-year students in their academic integration, the faculty organizes mid-term tests. These mid-term tests offer new students in the program a first realistic exam experience. The result of the mid-term tests is taken into account in the final course grade (25%), provided that the student passed the mid-term test and provided that the inclusion of the mid-term test grade improves the final grade. Based on a random assignment of tests to two student groups, only half of the Engineering Science students is assigned to the Applied Mechanics, part 1 mid-term test. All Engineering Science Architecture students take part in the mid-term test of Applied Mechanics, part 1 (no random assignment). In total, 355 students could participate to this mid-term test, which is a two-hour long multiple-choice test with 4-5 engineering problems to solve.

The Disciplinary Learning Companion was used to support students in their preparation for the mid-term test. A reflection exercise built around last year's mid-term test was provided on the Virtual Learning Environment of the course. In particular, a learning path was constructed consisting of four steps: 1) Solve the mid-term test of last year, 2) Compare your solution with the model solution, 3) Reflect using the Disciplinary Learning Companion, 4) Engage with the feedback, construct a plan, and/or request for help. Remark that students did not have to enter the Disciplinary Learning Companion to see last year's mid-term test, nor the solution.

The Disciplinary Learning Companion was implemented in the Qualtrics survey tool and structured around the five key dimensions highlighted in Section 2 with reflection questions focusing on the five dimensions of Strategy plan, Concepts, Mathematical Model, Computations, and Interpretation. For each of the five problems of the mid-term test, questions focusing on the above five dimensions were designed (in total 29 questions). In the Companion, for each problem, students get feedback based on their response. This feedback points to possible and typical errors, additional explanations in the course text, the model solution, ways to improve, etc. At the end,

overarching feedback was provided with a total score for each of the five dimensions and with pointers to additional help.

With the implementation of the pilot, we aim to answer the following research questions: From the **quantitative side**: What are the relations between 1) the scores of students on the five dimensions of the learning companion, 2) completion of the reflection module and achievement in the mid-term test, 3) completion of the reflection module and two learning skills: use of test strategies and motivation, and 4) students' score on the five dimensions in the companion and their achievement in the mid-term test. Motivation and use of test-strategies were measured using the LASSI survey at the beginning of the academic year. From the **qualitative side**: 1) What is the feasibility of developing a Disciplinary Learning Companion, and 2) What are teachers' views on the potential usefulness of a Disciplinary Learning Companion.

3.2 Methodology

We used a quantitative and qualitative approach to evaluate the pilot of the Disciplinary Learning Companion. Both analysis aimed at gaining better understanding on how to improve the companion for future use throughout an entire course. To answer **the quantitative** research questions, we tracked students' answers in the Disciplinary Learning Companion, and measured motivation and use of test-strategies using the LASSI survey that we administered at the beginning of the academic year.

To answer the **qualitative** research questions we set up three focus groups with teaching assistants (7 participants) and tutors (three participants). Unfortunately we did not manage to recruit students for the focus groups. The focus groups were transcribed and then analyzed using a thematic analysis by one of the principal investigators.

3.3 Quantitative findings

From the 355 students who could participate in the mid-term test, only 332 actually participated. From these students, only 47 (13%) entirely completed the Disciplinary Learning Companion in their preparation. (RQ1) We found that students' scores on Concepts and Mathematical model were positively correlated (Spearman $r(47)=0.46, p<0.0015$), as were the scores on the Strategy plan and the Concepts (Spearman $r(47)=0.34, p=0.02$). Other dimensions were not correlated. (RQ2) We found that students that completed the reflection module score significantly higher on the mid-term test compared to all students (Mann-Whitney, $p=0.028$). (RQ3) Completion of the companion was not correlated to students' motivation ($p=0.29$) nor use of test-strategies ($p=0.32$). (RQ4) We found no relation between students' scores on the mid-term test and companion score's on Strategy plan ($p=0.30$) and Concepts ($p=0.18$), the only two dimensions where we hypothesized a correlation.

3.4 Qualitative findings

For reporting purposes we refer to teaching assistants and tutors as TAs.

Time-investment: TAs stated that students will probably consider the module to be too time-consuming, and that it is better to spread the reflection over different

modules and over time. A positive aspect is that the module can be completed asynchronously.

Feedback: TAs indicated that the feedback contains too much repetition and should be more concise, e.g. referring with a pointer to repeating explanations. A strong point is that different solution strategies are shown in the feedback, but there could be even more room for different solution strategies. It was particularly appreciated that students got supportive messages when the answer was correct, while still stating “do you know why this is correct?” to offer some elaborations. The specificity of the feedback is important and could even be improved at some points. The feedback could focus more on how to obtain a better Strategy plan, Mathematical model, etc. It was considered a good point that the feedback contains pointers to the course text and that typical errors were provided, while the latter could still be improved.

Content: TA’s appreciated the emphasis on the methodological approach, which they are not always able to provide during the exercise sessions. This emphasis however might be “over the top” for simple problems. The fact that reflection questions were tailored to the specific problem was considered very good, but is expected to increase the work load to build such a module. Therefore there is a balance between specificity and work-load and transferability. The “Interpretation” dimension was considered very important. It would be an opportunity that student also reflect on how they would approach the problem in case of some small variations.

Platform and lay-out: TA’s stated that the implementation of the Disciplinary Learning Companion allows for a good combination of independent work and personal feedback and appreciate the interactivity. TA’s disagreed on whether the model solution should be offered as a whole before reflection (they get the overview) or that it should be integrated it in the reflection module (step-by-step and they are pushed to use the reflection module). Related to this, they also disagreed if it would be most optimal to first solve the problem and then reflect in the companion, or to solve the problem while reflecting in the companion. The five dimensions could also be readily recognized from the companion. TA’s disagreed on whether all five dimensions offer sufficient added value, some found all essential while others only found Strategy and Interpretation important. They all agreed that these five dimensions will only be useful for a student if they are also used in the exercise sessions, such that students can really understand these dimensions. The interface of the companion should be improved such that student can go back and forth in the reflection rather than forcing them to stay on a linear path. TA’s had some particular feedback regarding the visualization in the Learning Companion which is not elaborated further here. The reflection in the companion was very elaborate, which might scare away students, therefore one should pay attention to keep the companion lightweight enough. Finally, TA’s stated that the feedback should encourage students more to retry (a particular element of) the problem if they failed to solve it.

Integration in the course: TA’s disagreed on whether the reflection in the companion should be mandatory or not. It would be useful anyway to provide students with guidelines on when reflection is useful. Integration of the Learning Companion in the exercise sessions was considered to be very important: this could be done as part of the preparation of an exercise session. TAs considered this particularly important for first-year students who are suspected to not have enough intrinsic motivation and self-regulation to plan the reflection themselves. The

professors of the course should also indicate the importance of the reflection in the companion. Frequency and length have to be balanced: it should be frequent enough such that students generate a habit of completing the companion and substantial enough to show the importance, but it should be not too frequent or too long such that it does not overload the students. TA's stated that a more elaborate module before a test and shorter modules each week could offer a good balance.

Building new reflection modules: TA's indicated that they would be willing to build own reflection modules in the companion if proper guidelines and support are provided, and that they would also adapt the exercise sessions to more explicitly connect the solutions of problems to the five dimensions. However, they feared that it might be challenging to find the time to build specific reflection module connected to each exercise session. TA's found that the reflection should be an integral part of the entire program and not only of a single course, and that the importance of reflection should be emphasized more in the TA training.

Goal and purpose of the companion: TAs stated that the companion stimulates reflection skills that a student should obtain anyway and that it makes things that good students do spontaneously more explicit, such that weaker students can more easily learn this. TA's thought that only a small subset of students would spontaneously transfer the reflection to other courses even after using the companion, while repeated use of the companion might cause student to change their approach unconsciously. The companion is believed to offer guidance of students in their solution process, while the added value for students that can already solve the problem is possibly limited. TA's appreciated that the companion focuses on reflection and find this missing in other platforms such as Pearson's Mastering Physics. They found the companion to offer a good format for personal feedback and a good addition to model solutions, allowing to gain new insights without having to redo problems.

4 DISCUSSION, FUTURE WORK, AND CONCLUSION

This paper presented the ideas behind the Disciplinary Learning Companion, a first development of the Disciplinary Learning Companion, and a preliminary quantitative and qualitative analysis based on a small pilot. The first pilot only presented a limited set of evidence considering that the companion was just used for one reflection module, which also resulted in a minority of the students actually using it.

While the quantitative results indicated that use of the companion is correlated with academic achievement, we want by no means indicate a causal relation. In fact, we rather would state that this result merely shows that the learning companion probably attracted the students that are preparing better for the mid-term test, which therefore obtain on average a higher test score. The quantitative results point to the need for future research on the impact of the companion on reflection and learning. A particular point of attention is to investigate further if the score on the five dimensions of problem solving are related to learning, and could therefore provide a pointer for feedback to students and teachers.

With the qualitative results we can conclude that tutors and teaching assistants see the potential of the Disciplinary Learning Companion, and very importantly, see it feasible, provided proper support, to develop reflection modules themselves connected to particular problems they are teaching. Based on this promising results, and building on the points of improvement we are currently deploying an improved

version of the Disciplinary Learning throughout a full course of engineering mechanics, which allows us to further investigate our hypothesis of higher impact on learning with the Disciplinary Learning Companion compared to a non-disciplinary companion. At the same time, we are developing more visual feedback to students and teachers, including more high-level feedback on self-regulation and student's developments over time. This would allow to move in the direction of Learning Analytics Dashboards [5], similar to the EPFL Learning Companion [1].

REFERENCES

- [1] Tormey, R, Hardebolle, C., Pinto & Jermann, P. (2020) Designing for impact: a conceptual framework for learning analytics as self-assessment tools, *Assessment & Evaluation in Higher Education*, 45:6, 901-911.
- [2] Efklides, A. (2011). Interactions of metacognition with motivation and affect in self-regulated learning: The MASRL model. *Educational Psychologist*, 46(1), 6–25. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00461520.2011.538645>
- [3] Haller, E. P., D. A. Child, and H. J. Walberg. 1988. "Can Comprehension Be Taught? A Quantitative Synthesis of 'Metacognitive' Studies." *Educational Researcher* 17(9): 5
- [4] Dignath, C., and G. Büttner. 2008. "Components of Fostering Self-Regulated Learning among Students. A Meta-Analysis on Intervention Studies at Primary and Secondary School Level." *Metacognition and Learning* 3(3): 231–264.
- [5] Verbert, K., Duval, E., Klerkx, J., Govaerts, S., & Santos, J. L. (2013). Learning Analytics Dashboard Applications. *American Behavioral Scientist*, 57(10), 1500–1509. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0002764213479363>
- [6] Hattie, J., & Timperley, H. (2007). The Power of Feedback. *Review of Educational Research*, 77(1), 81–112. <https://doi.org/10.3102/003465430298487>
- [7] Streveler, R.A., Litzinger, T.A., Miller, R.L. and Steif, P.S. (2008), Learning Conceptual Knowledge in the Engineering Sciences: Overview and Future Research Directions. *Journal of Engineering Education*, 97: 279-294. <https://doi-org.kuleuven.ezproxy.kuleuven.be/10.1002/j.2168-9830.2008.tb00979.x>